

COVER SHEET FOR PROPOSAL TO THE NATIONAL SCIENCE FOUNDATION

PROGRAM ANNOUNCEMENT/SOLICITATION NO./CLOSING DATE/if not in response to a program announcement/solicitation enter NSF 07-140					FOR NSF USE ONLY	
FOR CONSIDERATION BY NSF ORGANIZATION UNIT(S) (Indicate the most specific unit known, i.e. program, division, etc.)					NSF PROPOSAL NUMBER	
ARC - ARCTIC RESRCH SUPPRT & LOGISTI					0741430	
DATE RECEIVED	NUMBER OF COPIES	DIVISION ASSIGNED	FUND CODE	DUNS# (Data Universal Numbering System)	FILE LOCATION	
06/16/2007	2	14010000 ARC	5205	796268548	06/16/2007 3:49am	
EMPLOYER IDENTIFICATION NUMBER (EIN) OR TAXPAYER IDENTIFICATION NUMBER (TIN)		SHOW PREVIOUS AWARD NO. IF THIS IS <input type="checkbox"/> A RENEWAL <input type="checkbox"/> AN ACCOMPLISHMENT-BASED RENEWAL		IS THIS PROPOSAL BEING SUBMITTED TO ANOTHER FEDERAL AGENCY? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> IF YES, LIST ACRONYM(S)		
		0101279				
NAME OF ORGANIZATION TO WHICH AWARD SHOULD BE MADE			ADDRESS OF AWARDEE ORGANIZATION, INCLUDING 9 DIGIT ZIP CODE			
Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.			Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.			
AWARDEE ORGANIZATION CODE (IF KNOWN)			3535 College Road, Suite 101			
5300001191			Fairbanks, AK. 997093710			
NAME OF PERFORMING ORGANIZATION, IF DIFFERENT FROM ABOVE			ADDRESS OF PERFORMING ORGANIZATION, IF DIFFERENT, INCLUDING 9 DIGIT ZIP CODE			
PERFORMING ORGANIZATION CODE (IF KNOWN)						
IS AWARDEE ORGANIZATION (Check All That Apply) (See GPG II.C For Definitions)			<input type="checkbox"/> SMALL BUSINESS <input type="checkbox"/> FOR-PROFIT ORGANIZATION		<input type="checkbox"/> MINORITY BUSINESS <input type="checkbox"/> WOMAN-OWNED BUSINESS	
					<input type="checkbox"/> IF THIS IS A PRELIMINARY PROPOSAL THEN CHECK HERE	
TITLE OF PROPOSED PROJECT Organizational Support to the U.S. Arctic Science Program						
REQUESTED AMOUNT \$ 816,200		PROPOSED DURATION (1-60 MONTHS) 3 months		REQUESTED STARTING DATE		SHOW RELATED PRELIMINARY PROPOSAL NO. IF APPLICABLE
CHECK APPROPRIATE BOX(ES) IF THIS PROPOSAL INCLUDES ANY OF THE ITEMS LISTED BELOW						
<input type="checkbox"/> BEGINNING INVESTIGATOR (GPG I.G.2)			<input type="checkbox"/> HUMAN SUBJECTS (GPG II.D.6) Human Subjects Assurance Number _____			
<input type="checkbox"/> DISCLOSURE OF LOBBYING ACTIVITIES (GPG II.C)			Exemption Subsection _____ or IRB App. Date _____			
<input type="checkbox"/> PROPRIETARY & PRIVILEGED INFORMATION (GPG I.D, II.C.1.d)			<input type="checkbox"/> INTERNATIONAL COOPERATIVE ACTIVITIES: COUNTRY/COUNTRIES INVOLVED (GPG II.C.2.j)			
<input type="checkbox"/> HISTORIC PLACES (GPG II.C.2.j)			_____			
<input type="checkbox"/> SMALL GRANT FOR EXPLOR. RESEARCH (SGER) (GPG II.D.1)			<input type="checkbox"/> HIGH RESOLUTION GRAPHICS/OTHER GRAPHICS WHERE EXACT COLOR REPRESENTATION IS REQUIRED FOR PROPER INTERPRETATION (GPG I.G.1)			
<input type="checkbox"/> VERTEBRATE ANIMALS (GPG II.D.5) IACUC App. Date _____						
PHS Animal Welfare Assurance Number _____						
PI/PD DEPARTMENT ARCUS		PI/PD POSTAL ADDRESS 3535 College Road, Suite 101				
PI/PD FAX NUMBER 907-474-1604		Fairbanks, AK 997093710				
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CERTIFICATION PAGE

Certification for Authorized Organizational Representative or Individual Applicant:

By signing and submitting this proposal, the Authorized Organizational Representative or Individual Applicant is: (1) certifying that statements made herein are true and complete to the best of his/her knowledge; and (2) agreeing to accept the obligation to comply with NSF award terms and conditions if an award is made as a result of this application. Further, the applicant is hereby providing certifications regarding debarment and suspension, drug-free workplace, and lobbying activities (see below), nondiscrimination, and flood hazard insurance (when applicable) as set forth in the NSF Proposal & Award Policies & Procedures Guide, Part I: the Grant Proposal Guide (GPG) (NSF 07-140). Willful provision of false information in this application and its supporting documents or in reports required under an ensuing award is a criminal offense (U. S. Code, Title 18, Section 1001).

Conflict of Interest Certification

In addition, if the applicant institution employs more than fifty persons, by electronically signing the NSF Proposal Cover Sheet, the Authorized Organizational Representative of the applicant institution is certifying that the institution has implemented a written and enforced conflict of interest policy that is consistent with the provisions of the NSF Proposal & Award Policies & Procedures Guide, Part II, Award & Administration Guide (AAG) Chapter IV.A; that to the best of his/her knowledge, all financial disclosures required by that conflict of interest policy have been made; and that all identified conflicts of interest will have been satisfactorily managed, reduced or eliminated prior to the institution's expenditure of any funds under the award, in accordance with the institution's conflict of interest policy. Conflicts which cannot be satisfactorily managed, reduced or eliminated must be disclosed to NSF.

Drug Free Work Place Certification

By electronically signing the NSF Proposal Cover Sheet, the Authorized Organizational Representative or Individual Applicant is providing the Drug Free Work Place Certification contained in Exhibit II-3 of the Grant Proposal Guide.

Debarment and Suspension Certification

(If answer "yes", please provide explanation.)

Is the organization or its principals presently debarred, suspended, proposed for debarment, declared ineligible, or voluntarily excluded from covered transactions by any Federal department or agency?

Yes

No

By electronically signing the NSF Proposal Cover Sheet, the Authorized Organizational Representative or Individual Applicant is providing the Debarment and Suspension Certification contained in Exhibit II-4 of the Grant Proposal Guide.

Certification Regarding Lobbying

The following certification is required for an award of a Federal contract, grant, or cooperative agreement exceeding \$100,000 and for an award of a Federal loan or a commitment providing for the United States to insure or guarantee a loan exceeding \$150,000.

Certification for Contracts, Grants, Loans and Cooperative Agreements

The undersigned certifies, to the best of his or her knowledge and belief, that:

- (1) No federal appropriated funds have been paid or will be paid, by or on behalf of the undersigned, to any person for influencing or attempting to influence an officer or employee of any agency, a Member of Congress, an officer or employee of Congress, or an employee of a Member of Congress in connection with the awarding of any federal contract, the making of any Federal grant, the making of any Federal loan, the entering into of any cooperative agreement, and the extension, continuation, renewal, amendment, or modification of any Federal contract, grant, loan, or cooperative agreement.
- (2) If any funds other than Federal appropriated funds have been paid or will be paid to any person for influencing or attempting to influence an officer or employee of any agency, a Member of Congress, an officer or employee of Congress, or an employee of a Member of Congress in connection with this Federal contract, grant, loan, or cooperative agreement, the undersigned shall complete and submit Standard Form-LLL, "Disclosure of Lobbying Activities," in accordance with its instructions.
- (3) The undersigned shall require that the language of this certification be included in the award documents for all subawards at all tiers including subcontracts, subgrants, and contracts under grants, loans, and cooperative agreements and that all subrecipients shall certify and disclose accordingly.

This certification is a material representation of fact upon which reliance was placed when this transaction was made or entered into. Submission of this certification is a prerequisite for making or entering into this transaction imposed by section 1352, Title 31, U.S. Code. Any person who fails to file the required certification shall be subject to a civil penalty of not less than \$10,000 and not more than \$100,000 for each such failure.

Certification Regarding Nondiscrimination

By electronically signing the NSF Proposal Cover Sheet, the Authorized Organizational Representative is providing the Certification Regarding Nondiscrimination contained in Exhibit II-6 of the Grant Proposal Guide.

Certification Regarding Flood Hazard Insurance

Two sections of the National Flood Insurance Act of 1968 (42 USC §4012a and §4106) bar Federal agencies from giving financial assistance for acquisition or construction purposes in any area identified by the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) as having special flood hazards unless the:

- (1) community in which that area is located participates in the national flood insurance program; and
- (2) building (and any related equipment) is covered by adequate flood insurance.

By electronically signing the NSF Proposal Cover Sheet, the Authorized Organizational Representative or Individual Applicant located in FEMA-designated special flood hazard areas is certifying that adequate flood insurance has been or will be obtained in the following situations:

- (1) for NSF grants for the construction of a building or facility, regardless of the dollar amount of the grant; and
- (2) for other NSF Grants when more than \$25,000 has been budgeted in the proposal for repair, alteration or improvement (construction) of a building or facility.

AUTHORIZED ORGANIZATIONAL REPRESENTATIVE		SIGNATURE	DATE
NAME Wendy K Warnick		Electronic Signature	Jun 16 2007 3:47AM
TELEPHONE NUMBER 907-474-1600	ELECTRONIC MAIL ADDRESS warnick@arcus.org	FAX NUMBER 907-474-1604	

*SUBMISSION OF SOCIAL SECURITY NUMBERS IS VOLUNTARY AND WILL NOT AFFECT THE ORGANIZATION'S ELIGIBILITY FOR AN AWARD. HOWEVER, THEY ARE AN INTEGRAL PART OF THE INFORMATION SYSTEM AND ASSIST IN PROCESSING THE PROPOSAL. SSN SOLICITED UNDER NSF ACT OF 1950, AS AMENDED.

This is a request for a supplement to ARCUS' cooperative agreement with the National Science Foundation (No. ARC-0101279). The supplement of \$816,200 to the funds already awarded is necessary to continue support of ongoing activities that are within the scope of the original agreement while details of a new cooperative agreement are negotiated. This supplement request also extends the expiration date of the award from 30 June 2007 to 30 September 2007 so that there will be no interruption of ongoing services and current tasking prior to a new award being made.

The activities described in this request for supplemental funds fall under the following major tasks identified in the cooperative agreement: 1) Arctic Community Science Planning; 2) NSF Division of Arctic Sciences Coordination; 3) Arctic Science Education; 4) Information and Outreach; and 5) Core Support. The activities described here provide community science management for NSF-funded research programs, coordinate research-focused community workshops and meetings, expand education and outreach opportunities for undergraduate and graduate students and for teachers and researchers, and provide important information to scientists, educators, and policy makers. All of the activities support community science planning or provide information and support for the conduct of arctic research.

Accomplishments between April 2006 and the present are outlined only for those activities for which supplemental funding is requested. This information is included to provide context for the work that ARCUS is doing through this cooperative agreement and the basis on which supplemental funding is requested. The projected activities between July and September 2007 for which supplemental funding is requested also are summarized. All activities described fall under the current scope and tasks of the existing cooperative agreement.

1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

1.4 Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) Planning and Coordination

As the SEARCH science management office, ARCUS has worked since 2005 with the NSF SEARCH Program Director, the SEARCH Interagency Program Management Committee (IPMC), SEARCH Science Steering Committee (SSC) Chair and members, and the international arctic research community to implement a number of development and planning activities on behalf of the SEARCH program. Since April 2006, these include convening an SSC meeting, coordinating with community and agency representatives to implement recommendations of the 2005 SEARCH Implementation Workshop, and assistance with developing international collaborations such as SEARCH IPY activities.

Accomplishments

- Worked with SSC and IPMC Chairs to organize and convene a SSC Meeting in Arlington, VA, in November 2006; agency personnel and members of the three SEARCH Panels also attended.
- Coordinated the creation and appointment, and facilitated activities of, three standing SEARCH Working Groups on Data Management, Paleoenvironment, and Education and Outreach.
- Worked with the SEARCH SSC Chair and IPMC to implement membership rotation for the SSC and support appropriate SSC science planning activities, including coordination with the developing Arctic Observing Network and International Polar Year efforts.

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- Facilitated activities of the three SEARCH panels (Observing, Understanding, and Responding to Change), including supporting planning activities specifically related to implementation of a SEARCH observing system.
 - Continued assistance with international coordination activities, including support of the Chair of the International ASOF Program and the developing partnership between SEARCH and the European Developing Arctic Modeling and Observing Capabilities for Long-term Environmental Studies (DAMOCLES).
 - Commenced planning for 2008 State of the Arctic Conference and began discussions on timing, focus, and content of conference.
 - Continued development of searchable online SEARCH Project Catalog to track and communicate SEARCH-funded and SEARCH-related research projects, initiatives, and programs, in consultation with an *ad hoc* committee.
 - Ongoing SEARCH website development and updates.

Planned Activities

The requested supplemental funding will support several continuing SEARCH planning and coordination activities, including:

- Continued development of the SEARCH Project Catalog.
- Development of a website, within the SEARCH website, for the Arctic Observing Network, a major implementation of the SEARCH Observing Change scientific priorities.
- Geo-referencing and extracting geographic coordinates of locations for priority SEARCH observation activities, as depicted in the maps in the 2005 report *Study of Environmental Arctic Change: Plans for Implementation During the International Polar Year and Beyond*, for use by the Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC) staff in the drafting of the next biennial revision of the Arctic Research Plan, which will focus on the development of the Arctic Observing Network in the context of SEARCH.
- Planning, convening, and staffing the 2007 SEARCH SSC meeting, including participant travel support. In addition to the members of the SSC, participants will include the three implementation panel chairs and several additional participants invited to address specific topics germane to SEARCH planning and SSC discussions.
- Travel support for the SEARCH SSC Chair.
- Planning for the 2008 State of the Arctic conference.
- Other project office tasks such as teleconferences and eMeetings, as necessary.

1.5 Bering Ecosystem Research Program Planning and Coordination

For the past several years the NSF Division of Arctic Sciences has supported the Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST), a planning process to initiate collaborative studies of the sub-arctic seas, culminating in cooperative ecological research of the eastern, western, and basin areas by Japan, Russia and the United States. ARCUS provides organizational support and coordination of activities for the BEST science planning process, including support for the BEST Science Steering Committee (SSC) and coordination with the BEST planning office at the University of Washington. BEST priorities for research, published in the BEST science plan in 2004, were included in the fall 2005 NSF Division of Arctic Sciences announcement of opportunity; awards through this opportunity were announced in July 2006. ARCUS has provided continuing organizational support to the program, including convening a meeting in

July 2006 of multiple agencies with research interests in the Bering Sea and a meeting in September 2006 of funded BEST principal investigators. Tasks have also included coordination and support for representatives of the program to attend a number of relevant meetings.

The requested supplemental funding will support a minimal amount of staff time for editing and publishing *Sustaining the Bering Ecosystem: A Social Sciences Research Plan*, and limited travel support for program representatives. The budget for the editing and publication of the research plan is included under Arctic Social Sciences Program Coordination, activity 2.3.4, Bering Sea Community Planning.

Accomplishments

- In close collaboration with the BEST SSC, the NSF program officer, and other agency representatives, ARCUS planned, convened, and staffed a meeting in July 2006 of multiple entities with research interests in the Bering Sea: the BEST SSC, the Bering Interagency Working Group, and the Bering Interagency Oversight Group. The meeting was held on the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) campus in Seattle, Washington. 34 invited participants attended, and about 15 NOAA personnel attended portions of the sessions.
- Planned, convened, and staffed a meeting of funded BEST Principal Investigators and representatives of the BEST SSC in September 2006 in Arlington, VA, to coordinate the development of an integrated research program and to guide fieldwork.
- Coordinated travel arrangements and provided materials and travel support for PIs or representatives of the BEST SSC to attend a number of relevant meetings, including the PICES-Ecosystems of Sub-arctic Seas (ESSAS) workshop in St. Petersburg, Russia (June 2006), the Calista Elders Council in Bethel, Alaska (January 2007), the Alaska Marine Science Symposium in Anchorage, Alaska (January 2007), the American Society for Limnology and Oceanography in Santa Fe, New Mexico (February 2007), the Alaska Forum on the Environment in Anchorage, Alaska (February 2007), and the ESSAS workshop in Hakodate, Japan (June 2007).

Planned Activities

- Editing, publication, and dissemination of BEST social science plan, in close collaboration with members of the organizing committee. The costs dedicated to completing and publishing the science plan are included in the budget under Arctic Social Sciences Program, activity 2.3.4, Bering Sea Community Planning.
- Ongoing distribution of the BEST science and implementation plans and website maintenance and updating.

2. NSF DIVISION OF ARCTIC SCIENCES COORDINATION

ARCUS provides organizational support and science planning coordination and facilitates research community planning activities for the NSF Division of Arctic Sciences. The additional activities planned under this major task are in support of the Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program.

2.2 ARCSS Program Coordination

ARCUS continues to provide community science management and coordination of activities for the NSF Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program. With the guidance of the ARCSS Committee, the ARCSS Program is in transition from a focus on synthesis activities to targeted thematic efforts addressing arctic system issues. Program coordination activities reported below have been designed to sustain an effective synthesis effort and facilitate a smooth transition to new activities by fostering high levels of community input and strong interdisciplinary collaboration.

The requested supplementary funds will support: development of the report from the April 2007 ARCSS-sponsored workshop *Arctic System Synthesis Workshop: New Perspectives through Data Discovery and Modeling*, planning and convening three community workshops, providing support for specific program coordination activities through subcontracts, and ongoing science management office activities such as eTown meetings, teleconferences, and website maintenance.

Accomplishments

- Worked with the ARCSS Committee to organize and convene two online "eTown Meetings:" one in September 2006 to solicit community input on the ARCSS science planning process, attended by 50 participants, and one in March 2007 to discuss priorities and strategies for ARCSS data management for promoting arctic system-level understanding and synthesis, attended by 48 participants.
- Organized the ARCSS Committee face-to-face meeting in November 2006; worked with the ARCSS Committee Executive Committee and NSF Program Director to develop the agenda, meeting materials, and facilitate meeting discussions.
- Supported three ARCSS meetings of opportunity at the 2006 American Geophysical Union (AGU) Conference in San Francisco through logistics, organizational, and website assistance.
- Supported emerging Communities of Practice—groups of researchers organized around a set of arctic system science questions—with planning and community development, including teleconference/webconference support and creation of online collaboration tools.
- Provided support for the group of funded Synthesis of Arctic System Science (SASS) projects/investigators, including support of individual project teleconferences, organization of several online meetings, and planning and providing materials for a special session at AGU in December 2006.
- Provided support for group of funded Study of the Northern Alaska Coastal System (SNACS) projects, including implementing a subcontract with the Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory (CRREL) to support a SNACS synthesis coordinator, updating and hosting of website, planning and providing materials for a special session at AGU in December 2006, and other meeting planning assistance.
- Provided support and guidance, through a subcontract with the University of Alaska Fairbanks, for a Human Dimensions of the Arctic System (HARC) project office to promote community development and coordinate human dimension research activities relevant to arctic system research.

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- Organized and convened several ARCSS Committee teleconferences on topics such as science planning, synthesis, and data management.
 - Supported and assisted the ARCSS Committee chair in planning, guiding, advising and leading the ARCSS Program community science planning and synthesis process.
 - In collaboration with the ARCSS Committee, NSF ARCSS Program Director, SEARCH Program leadership, and the International Arctic Research Center, convened and supported a three-day workshop on developing a coordinated data and modeling strategy to enhance arctic system synthesis. The workshop, *Arctic System Synthesis Workshop: New Perspectives through Data Discovery and Modeling*, was held 2-4 April 2007 in Seattle, WA. The 58 in-person participants represented a variety of expertise and disciplines, including perspectives on: natural, social, and physical sciences; field-based, remote sensing, and modeling approaches; data management; science-policy linkages; and education and outreach. In addition, nearly 35 additional community members participated online through a webcast and online bulletin board.
 - In collaboration with the ARCSS Committee and NSF Program Director, organized and convened the May 2007 ARCSS Committee Meeting in Washington, DC.
 - Organized and facilitated a meeting in May 2007 with representatives from the ARCSS Committee, the workshop organizing committee, and NSF program managers to brief NSF staff on the recommendations from *Arctic System Synthesis Workshop: New Perspectives through Data Discovery and Modeling*.
 - Participated in the 5th Annual NSF-ARCSS Freshwater Integration study (FWI) All-Hands Meeting, held in June 2007 in Bodega Bay, California. The meeting, which was attended by FWI Investigators, their graduate and undergraduate students, and other research community members, focused on sharing key findings, synthesizing results across projects and disciplines, and planning for new opportunities.

Planned Activities

- Follow-up on the data and modeling workshop's results with Organizing Committee and ARCSS Committee teleconferences and provide staff support to develop and publish the community-reviewed workshop report.
- Plan, convene, and staff three ARCSS workshops:
 - Investigators from the Study of the Northern Alaska Coastal System (SNACS) projects will meet in August 2007 to pursue synthesis and integration of SNACS research results in the final year of funded SNACS research.
 - The funded Synthesis of Arctic System Science (SASS) investigators will meet in September 2007 to discuss project plans and preliminary results, and to determine methods, approaches, and an organizational structure to advance cross-project integration and synthesis.
 - A community workshop in September 2007 will bring together researchers interested in contributing to the goals of the emerging Surface Transformations in the Arctic Environment (STATE) effort, an ARCSS Community of Practice (Co-oP) that has matured to its implementation phase. The planned workshop will result in community consensus on STATE's specific scientific objectives, priorities, and recommended implementation strategies.

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- Ongoing science management office activities such as organization and support of community eTown Meetings, teleconferences, and website maintenance.
 - Providing support for specific program coordination activities through subcontracts, as follows: salary support for the ARCSS Committee chair (University of California, Santa Barbara), the SNACS synthesis coordinator (Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory), and the HARC project office (University of Alaska Fairbanks).

3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series

ARCUS implemented the Arctic Visiting Speakers' (AVS) Series in January 2000 to increase communication and collaboration among the dispersed arctic research community, to nurture understanding and communication between arctic researchers and arctic community residents, and to improve public understanding of arctic research.

The program accomplishments since April 2006 and planned activities from now through September 2007 are listed below. The supplemental funds requested would support Arctic Visiting Speakers' tours from July through September 2007.

Accomplishments

- Twelve AVS tours have taken place since April 2006, addressing arctic issues at 40 different events. Speakers presented at a variety of venues including visitor centers, museums, schools, workshops, cultural festivals, and on the radio.
- Over 1400 people attended the public presentations.
- Of the twelve speaking tours, ten U.S. speakers visited institutions within the U.S. and two U.S. speakers traveled to Finland and Norway to lecture.
- Topics included the measurement of greenhouse gases in Alaska, permafrost, the state of climate change science, Native perspectives on western science and environmentalism, history and culture of Vikings, traditional wisdom and marine mammals in the context of climate change and industrialized fishing, multiculturalism in the European Arctic, the environmental fate of trace metals in the Arctic, and Healy-Oden Trans-Arctic Expedition (HOTRAX).
- Ten new speakers were added to the Speaker's Bureau, which currently has 62 profiles for potential Arctic Visiting Speakers.
- Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series brochures were distributed at various conferences.

Planned Activities

- Support up to four additional speaker tours through September 2007.
- Continue to promote the use of the Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series to facilitate collaboration and information sharing about arctic research and the Arctic, including distribution of program information via ArcticInfo.
- Advertise the AVS series extensively among arctic residents; encourage participation by indigenous experts as visiting speakers and by arctic communities as host institutions.
- Post AVS information to several educational e-mail listserves around the country to stimulate interest from the K–12 education community to apply as host institutions.

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- Continue to recruit individuals for the Speakers' Bureau.
 - Continue to provide updated information about speaker tours on the ARCUS website.
 - Post presentation videos and other materials sent to ARCUS by host institutions and speakers on the Internet Media Archive.

3.5 PolarTREC (Teachers and Researchers Exploring and Collaborating)

The PolarTREC (Teachers and Researchers Exploring and Collaborating) program is an educational research experience in which K-12 teachers participate in polar research, working closely with scientists as a pathway to improving science education through teachers' experiences in scientific inquiry. Participating teachers serve as a foundation for a growing community of students, educators, researchers and the general public that is engaged in science teaching and learning. Through PolarTREC, teachers have the opportunity to increase their knowledge, enhance teaching skills, transfer their experiences to the classroom, engage in leadership roles, and develop a supportive network of researchers and education colleagues. NSF has awarded funds to ARCUS to support 36 PolarTREC expeditions for three years (2007–2009) through award ESI-0632401; funding is requested through the cooperative agreement supplement to support coordination of additional science education activities related to PolarTREC that will extend the influence and accessibility of the program, but which are not funded through the PolarTREC grant. These activities include staff support and travel for several researcher/teacher visits, additional school participation, and community networking.

Planned Activities

- Support teacher/researcher teams in planning and implementing education and outreach activities before, during, and after the field expedition.
- Limited travel support for researchers to visit classrooms.

4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

4.1 *Witness the Arctic* Newsletter

Witness the Arctic is a biannual newsletter, available online and in hardcopy, that provides information on current arctic research and education efforts and news, significant research initiatives, national policy affecting arctic science, research support and logistics, profiles of institutions with major arctic research efforts, and calendar events and publications. With edited contributions from representatives throughout the arctic research and education community, *Witness the Arctic* is a substantive and significant source of information.

The accomplishments since April 2006 and planned activities from now through September 2007 are listed below. Supplemental funding will support the newsletter planning and development from July through September 2007.

Accomplishments

- Completed the Spring 2006 (Volume 12, number 1) issue of the newsletter. Distributed to 6,100 U.S. and 4,000 international subscribers. The newsletter featured an article on closing the gap between scientific research and education, as well as the standard sections on NSF programs and activities, science news, and international news.

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- In addition to the initial distribution to subscribers, the electronic version was posted on the ARCUS website for download; hard copies are available and distributed in response to requests.
 - Completed the Spring 2007 (Volume 12, number 2) issue in May 2007. The feature article for this issue is on the history of the International Polar Years. Estimated distribution will be to 7,500 U.S. and 4,800 international subscribers; the electronic version is available for download.

Planned activities

- Begin work on Volume 13, number 1. Determine feature story topic, solicit contributions for all sections, edit submissions, and draft material for this issue. Expected publication date is March 2008.

4.2 Website/Internet Resources

The ARCUS website provides essential information and resources for the diverse and geographically distributed arctic research community and serves over 6,000 files from over 2,000 pages. The website is the focal point for web-served educational programs such as PolarTREC, various community science planning tools, and provides important information and resources to the research community about key research programs, meetings, community activities, and publications. The ARCUS website represents a valuable source of information for the general public about arctic research, a forum for scientific exchange among arctic researchers, approaches for integrating arctic research with educational programs, and access to other researchers, programs, and stakeholders working in the Arctic.

The accomplishments since April 2006 and planned activities from now through September 2007 are listed below. The supplemental funds requested would support ongoing website development, management, and maintenance from July through September 2007.

Accomplishments

- Created, maintained, and updated sections of the website for ARCUS-facilitated programs, meetings, and workshops described in other activity descriptions in this report.
- Posted on-line versions of various arctic research publications for community access and downloading.
- Improved file structure and site architecture for major sections of the website.
- Developed additional stylesheets for improved consistency in visual layout.
- Implemented new technology and software for bulletin board applications for improved security and user functionality.
- Improved database-driven solutions (using SQL and PHP) with improved searchability and data sorting functionality for use in applications such as the Internet Media Archive, searchable project databases and a publication database.
- Continued to improve accessibility standards and code-compliance throughout the website.
- Transitioned the online Calendar maintained by ARCUS to a collaborative Arctic Calendar, working jointly with the International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) and the Arctic Ocean Sciences Board.

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- Developed an online calendar event submission process, with an underlying database that can be accessed and managed by any of the collaborating organizations.
 - Designed and implemented a unifying Arctic Calendar banner and footer that includes the logos of the sponsoring organizations and that can be used on linking or forwarding web pages on collaborating websites.
 - Made final design and function revisions to the Arctic Calendar website and database to fully implement the joint Arctic Calendar.

Planned Activities

- Announce the availability of the collaborative Arctic Calendar to the research community.
- Continue ongoing improvements to file structure and site architecture for efficient management of website.
- Continue ongoing development of database and community workspace tools as needed for a variety of programs and activities.
- Develop design and code standards to increase consistency throughout sections of the website.
- Develop and update content as needed.

4.3 ArcticInfo Listserver

ARCUS developed and manages the ArcticInfo Listserver, a "broadcast only" list with high quality, accuracy-checked, and well-edited content that provides information and important announcements to the international arctic research community. There have been 2,934 announcements distributed from ArcticInfo since its creation in September 1996. Each year has seen an increase in submissions for distribution and in subscribers. Currently about half of the subscribers are from the United States and half from other countries.

The accomplishments since April 2006 and planned activities from now through September 2007 are listed below. The supplemental funds requested would support ongoing management and maintenance from July through September 2007.

Accomplishments

- Received, reviewed, accepted or declined, edited, and formatted over 700 submissions to ArcticInfo.
- Distributed 588 announcements from April 2006 to present, including notices on funding opportunities, important events, publications, and position announcements. On average, approximately 40 announcements were posted per month.
- Communicated with subscribers regarding announcements, special information requests, subscribe or unsubscribe requests, and other concerns.
- Maintained a searchable online archive of all posted announcements.
- The listserv had 555 new subscribers in this period, resulting in 5,675 current subscribers.
- Maintained a database to track subscription activity.

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- Managed the "bounce list" by researching bounced announcements to correct and update addresses, investigate apparently dead domains, and delete addresses that consistently bounced back from the subscriber list.
 - In addition to managing ArcticInfo, ARCUS has created and manages 17 additional electronic lists for the arctic research community. These lists range from small group lists for community planning groups or science steering committees to large "community of researcher" lists, similar to but less comprehensive than ArcticInfo. Some of the lists are "participatory," meaning that any subscribed participant can post to the lists, and some are "broadcast only," meaning that only designated people can post content to the lists.

Planned Activities

- Continue to review, edit, and format ArcticInfo submissions. Post new announcements to the list and add them to the online archive.
- Continue to communicate with subscribers and organizations and individuals who wish to use the list for information distribution or access.
- Continue to track subscription activity and research "bounced" addresses.
- Continue advertising, maintenance, and management of the list.
- Continue to manage the additional arctic research community lists and develop additional lists, as needed and requested.

4.4 Directory of Arctic Researchers

The Directory of Arctic Researchers was initiated in 1994 to aid links among individual investigators, institutions, funding agencies, and arctic stakeholders and to facilitate arctic research and education efforts. The contents of the directory have been developed through extensive surveys of individual arctic researchers and institutions.

The accomplishments since April 2006 and planned activities from now through September 2007 are listed below. The supplemental funds requested would support ongoing management and maintenance of the Directory from July through September 2007.

Accomplishments

- Added 153 new records since April 2006. Presently there are a total of 4114 individual records in the Directory.
- Surveyed researchers with current Directory records to obtain updated contact and current research information. Surveyed significant international research organizations and individuals to expand non-U.S. researcher records in the database.
- Maintained and regularly updated a downloadable PDF of the Directory, including alphabetically listed individual researcher entries and a cross-reference file listing researchers within science specialty categories. Developed a new Directory PDF design and creation process, which streamlined the PDF creation and results in a smaller file size.
- Developed a customized PDF creation option, which allows users to easily create a customized PDF of their Directory search returns.

Planned Activities

- Begin discussions to design and develop web services to allow interactions (pulling and pushing information) with other arctic databases such as the CEON-IMS, Barrow Area Information Database-Internet Map Server, the VECO Polar Resources ARLSS project database, and ARMAP.
- Continue maintenance and expansion of the on-line Directory.

4.5 Internet Media Archive

The ARCUS Internet Media Archive (IMA) is a collection of photos, graphics, videos, and presentations that have been compiled for various purposes and are now shared through the Internet via the IMA. The contents of the IMA are organized by the contributor's name, by event, or by organization. All of the media available in the archive are accompanied by information about the content, the contributor or source, and usage requirements.

The accomplishments since April 2006 and planned activities from now through September 2007 are listed below. The supplemental funds requested would support ongoing management and maintenance of the Internet Media Archive from July through September 2007.

Accomplishments

- Since April 2006, 3262 files have been added to the Internet Media Archive, which currently contains 6249 photos and other media resources available to the public in 103 albums and 35 categories. These resources have been viewed 63,669 times. An additional approximately 8,500 resources in the archive are not yet publicly available; further documentation is being entered or gathered for these resources and when the information is complete they also will become publicly accessible.
- Most of the extensive ARCUS collection of audio and video resources from various workshops, meetings, and education and outreach activities from 2001 to the present has been archived on the IMA.
- Posted all photos for which permission has been received to the online archive, with detailed photo information, photographer contact information, use criteria, and keywords for the search interface.

Planned Activities

- Periodically remind the research community of the availability of the Internet Media Archive via ArcticInfo and other listserves.
- Continue to gather and add to the collection of arctic-related images and other media resources and continue research and data entry of relevant information about source, subject, dates, research project, and funding source for all of the images.
- Maintain communication with the contributors and potential contributors to solicit contributions and timely and detailed information about the media resources.
- Continue video- and audio-recording of relevant meetings, workshops, and programmatic activities for inclusion in the Internet Media Archive.

4.6 Arctic Community Outreach

ARCUS conducts a number of outreach activities that disseminate timely information about arctic research to scientists, policy and decision-makers, educators and the public, and that build supportive networks among those groups to advance international arctic research efforts and our understanding of the Arctic as a region.

The accomplishments since April 2006 and planned activities from now through September 2007 are listed below. The supplemental funds requested would support outreach activities from July through September 2007.

Accomplishments

- Planned and hosted the 1.5-day *Arctic Forum* conference in conjunction with ARCUS' 18th Annual Meeting in Washington, D.C. in May 2006. The topic of the *Forum* was "International Arctic Research at a Turning Point: Innovations and Collaborations for the Future," a theme that directly built on the topic and success of *Arctic Forum 2005*. The *Forum* was co-chaired by Dr. Craig Tweedie of the University of Texas El Paso and Dr. Volker Rachold of the International Arctic Science Committee. A two-minute video was developed by ARCUS staff in Spring 2006 with material from past *Arctic Forum* sessions to advertise *Arctic Forum 2006* and was distributed via the ARCUS website. *Arctic Forum 2006* was announced to the international arctic research community and registration and abstract submissions solicited via ArcticInfo and *Witness the Arctic*.
 - *Arctic Forum 2006* attracted 136 participants and included arctic researchers from the U.S. and nine other countries, policy makers, media representatives, federal agency personnel, and arctic residents, including significant representation from indigenous arctic communities.
 - The *Forum* was video-streamed via the Internet and followed by an international audience beyond those in attendance in Washington, D.C. Participants viewing the *Forum* via the video-stream were able to email questions and comments for the presenters to the co-chairs and ARCUS staff for inclusion in session discussions.
 - Plenary, panel, and poster presentations and discussions addressed topics such as: challenges and needs of system scale science; challenges and needs of stakeholder and community partnerships; broadening the legacy of the International Polar Year; and advancing arctic research through policy and science advocacy.
 - Presentations from the meeting are available on the ARCUS *Arctic Forum* website as downloadable Powerpoint or PDF files. Edited video and audio files from the *Arctic Forum 2006* presentations and sessions are available on the Internet Media Archive.
 - Published and distributed the 2006 *Arctic Forum* abstract volume.
- Developed information resources such as flyers, brochures, and posters regarding arctic research activities and priorities; participated in outreach activities at scientific meetings and workshops to inform the broader scientific community and policy and decision-makers about important arctic research efforts and findings.

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- Participated in or sponsored arctic outreach activities at the October 2006 AAAS Arctic Science Conference in Fairbanks, Alaska, the Fall 2006 Meeting of AGU in San Francisco, California, and at other relevant meetings and workshops.
 - Organized and convened a 1.5-day *Arctic Forum* in conjunction with ARCUS' 19th Annual Meeting in Washington, DC in May 2007, and co-hosted by the Embassy of Sweden. The focus of the *Arctic Forum 2007* was "Water in the Arctic: International Collaborations and Understanding Environmental Change." The *Arctic Forum* was timed to coincide with a special program at the Embassy of Sweden on "Water and Environment," which offered reflections on global, national, regional, and local perspectives regarding water. The *Arctic Forum 2007* was co-chaired by Larry Hinzman, University of Alaska Fairbanks, and Gunhild Rosqvist, Stockholm University.
 - *Arctic Forum 2007* attracted 137 participants and included arctic researchers from the U.S. and seven other countries, policy makers, media representatives, federal agency personnel, and arctic residents.
 - The *Forum* was video-streamed via the Internet and followed by an international audience beyond those in attendance in Washington, D.C. Participants viewing the *Forum* via the video-stream were able to post questions and comments for the presenters to an online bulletin board that could be displayed on the screen during the sessions.
 - Forum sessions included a diverse and international range of perspectives on the state of knowledge of the hydrological cycle in the circumpolar Arctic, gaps in our knowledge, and research and policy opportunities and priorities. Sessions also highlighted international collaborations for the International Polar Year and beyond.
 - Plenary, panel, and poster presentations and discussions addressed topics such as:
 - a. What are the changes being witnessed in the water cycle and how will these changes impact the physical, biological, and social environments of the Arctic?
 - b. How does the science of water and the arctic environment relate to public policy and how can information be translated to decision makers?
 - c. How can we forge international collaborations during IPY and beyond to address these exciting scientific challenges and opportunities?
 - d. What are the critical scientific and policy issues with regard to "Water in the Arctic," particularly those related to international collaboration?
 - e. What is the relationship between water and security, including national/political security issues, access to food and natural resources, and cultural sustainability?
 - f. What is the most important result, scientific or otherwise, that could come out of IPY? What is the single most important factor to ensure a successful IPY?
 - Six young investigators attended the *Arctic Forum 2007* with support from the Student Travel Scholarship Program co-sponsored by ARCUS and the Arctic CHAMP (Community-wide Hydrologic Analysis and Monitoring Program) Science Management Office. The travel scholarship competition was open internationally to Masters and PhD students working in a field related to the

Arctic Forum's focus on water and the arctic environment. The scholarship included airfare, lodging, and per diem. Successful applicants presented a poster at the *Arctic Forum*.

- Presentations from the meeting are available on the *ARCUS Arctic Forum* website as downloadable Powerpoint or PDF files. The unedited archive footage of *Arctic Forum* sessions also is available on the website.
- In association with the 2007 *Arctic Forum*, organized and convened a Congressional Briefing on "Observing, Understanding, and Responding to Arctic Change" on 22 May 2007 at the Russell Senate Office Building. Arctic researchers Donald Perovich, Mark Serreze, Andrea Lloyd, and Maribeth Murray presented information on observed changes that are ongoing in the Arctic, as well as scientific advances that help us understand and respond to those changes. The briefing included discussion of practical challenges, opportunities, and policy implications associated with climate change, including coastal erosion, infrastructure damage, and social issues such as transportation and subsistence. Forty participants attending the briefing, including congressional staff members, agency staff, and others.

Planned Activities

- Edit the video and audio files from the *Arctic Forum 2007* presentations and sessions for posting as downloadable content in the Internet Media Archive.
- Prepare posters or presentations on request and participate in scientific meetings or workshops to provide information and outreach regarding arctic research activities, needs, and priorities.

5. CORE SUPPORT

Core support provides management and infrastructure crucial to support the overall tasks and the projects and activities included in each task of the cooperative agreement. This category was initiated to ensure stability and continuity of the direct activities that support the whole of the cooperative agreement so they are not vulnerable to the changes in the specific tasks and activities funded from year-to-year throughout the agreement.

ARCUS is a relatively small non-profit organization, and the Executive Director is closely involved in all activities of the organization including planning, prioritizing, managing, and directly implementing the work undertaken on behalf of the National Science Foundation. The Executive Director works closely with ARCUS project managers to prioritize tasks with respect to annual and longer-term plans and to manage individual workloads and projects. She closely reviews activities and products and ensures that projects are completed as scheduled and in accordance with the annual plan and that the products or effects of the activities are beneficial to arctic research and to the goals of the particular task funded through the cooperative agreement. She is directly involved in working with science steering committees and research community contributors to ensure that projects are concluded effectively and in a timely fashion. The Executive Director also works closely with the ARCUS Business Manager in budgeting and reviewing ongoing project expenditures against the NSF budget. The Executive Director liaises directly with NSF on all planning,

programmatic, and budget issues. This component of management is essential to the ongoing work ARCUS carries out on behalf of the NSF.

Similarly, the Systems Administrator manages the network, server, and all technical needs required to support NSF tasks and project activities. He works directly with the Executive Director to ensure that all hardware and software requirements are met so that server and network operations supporting NSF activities are carried out smoothly and efficiently. The Executive Director and Systems Administrator plan for upcoming needs, including scientific meetings and conferences convened by ARCUS on behalf of the NSF, in conjunction with the annual program plan.

While the work of both these positions is directly related to the successful implementation of NSF activities and projects, it is more difficult to allocate much of this time specifically to any one individual project, hence the use of Core Support to collect these direct management costs. Other costs charged to Core Support include direct system infrastructure (computer hardware and software required to maintain the network and server for the databases and listserves that support NSF-funded activities), high-speed Internet, and the development necessary to continuously maintain the level of service committed to the arctic research community under the cooperative agreement.

The major accomplishments since April 2006 and planned activities from now through September 2007 are listed below. The supplemental funds requested would support Core activities from July through September 2007.

Accomplishments

- Coordinated planning, managed emerging priorities, and supervised work on all the tasks and project activities described in this report. The portion of the Executive Director's time dedicated to project activities funded through this agreement is charged to the Core Support category rather than to individual projects.
- Upgraded hardware, software, and programming to expand capability for projects that require expanded server, network, and database capacity, support for NSF-sponsored meeting online registration, poster submission, and general information distribution.
- Managed the server setup, network, creation of needed technical resources, and the computing capability that directly supports the project activities. The portion of the System Administrator's time dedicated to project activities funded through this agreement is charged to the Core Support category. System upgrades included:
 - Performed Web server backend upgrades for PHP and MySQL plus applications relying on those packages.
 - Overhauled the email server spam prevention system, switching to the ASSP (Anti-Spam SMTP Proxy) software.
 - Overhauled and expanded the network backup system, including software upgrades and adding a backup server to greatly expand capacity.
 - Created multiple new email lists on the List Server machine and performed minor software upgrades on the server.

-
- Replaced the Flexmail web email form processor (concerns included security and performance issues) with custom-built PHP form processor.
 - Performed a number of other software and hardware upgrades to increase system and network efficiency and security.
 - Researched, purchased, and set up an Epson 9600 large format printer, used for printing posters and banners for NSF-funded projects. The on-site availability of the large format printer has considerably reduced the cost of producing posters for various projects.
 - Supported staff travel to arctic research meetings and workshops that addressed topics pertaining to multiple NSF projects and activities included in the cooperative agreement, but which were not specific to one project.

Planned Activities

- Coordinate planning, prioritization and supervision of work on all the tasks and projects described in the projected activities, the program plan and budget for the remainder of the duration of this cooperative agreement. The portion of the Executive Director's time dedicated to project activities funded through this agreement will be charged to the Core Support category.
- Continue to research and upgrade hardware, software, and programming required to expand the interactive and dynamic capabilities of such projects as SEARCH, the ARCSS Program, the Arctic Social Sciences Program, the Directory of Arctic Researchers, ArcticInfo, the collaborative Arctic Calendar, the Internet Media Archive, interactive real-time online seminars and meetings, interactive bulletin boards, meeting registration, abstract submission, streamed audio/video content, and general information.
- Manage the server setup, network, and creation of needed technical resources and the computing capability that directly supports the project activities. The portion of the System Administrator's time dedicated to direct activities funded through this agreement will be charged to the Core Support category.
- Support staff participation at arctic research meetings and workshops on topics pertaining to multiple NSF projects and activities included in the cooperative agreement, but which are not specific to one project.

SUMMARY

ARCUS has facilitated scientific planning for arctic research efforts for over fifteen years by working with the scientific community through surveys, workshops, Internet communications, and other means to define science priorities and research initiatives. ARCUS has organized dozens of workshops and published numerous scientific planning documents that reflect the recommendations of the arctic research community on scientific priorities in various research fields. All of the activities described in this request for supplemental funds support the community science planning process for the NSF Division of Arctic Sciences and provide information and support for the conduct of arctic research and, therefore, will contribute to the overall excellence and advancement of arctic research supported by the National Science Foundation.

Supplement Request Justification

This supplement of \$816,200 to ARCUS' cooperative agreement with the National Science Foundation (No. ARC-0101279) is necessary to continue support of ongoing activities that are within the scope of the original agreement while details of a new cooperative agreement are negotiated. This supplement request also extends the expiration date of the award from 30 June 2007 to 30 September 2007 so that there will be no interruption of ongoing services and current tasking prior to a new award being made.

All of the activities described in the Summary of Proposed Work and the Budget Justification are in keeping with, and part of, ARCUS' work with the National Science Foundation to provide organizational support for the U.S. arctic science programs. The specific activities and the support that will be provided have been discussed with the NSF managing program officer. All activities are within the scope of the current cooperative agreement and are described in detail in the Summary of Proposed Work.

ARCUS submitted a proposal for a five-year cooperative agreement (CA) on 24 January 2006; we understand that NSF has completed the review process and intends to recommend a new cooperative agreement with ARCUS. The NSF Office of Polar Programs (OPP) is negotiating the budget details of a new CA with ARCUS and, for the first time, the Division of Arctic Sciences will need to take the ARCUS CA proposal to the Directors Review Board (DRB) for approval, due to a reduction in the amount of the DRB threshold.

The managing program officer notified ARCUS on 4 June 2007 that the process would not be completed in time to seamlessly transition ARCUS to a new CA. It is important to ARCUS and OPP that ARCUS continue progress on current tasking while the new CA is negotiated. The managing program officer requested that ARCUS submit a request for a three-month supplemental budget to extend the existing CA to the date when a new CA will be awarded so that there will be no interruption of ongoing services and current tasking.

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET YEAR 1

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR Wendy K Warnick				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PI, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-months		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
	CAL	ACAD	SUMR				
1. Wendy K Warnick - Executive Director	2.50	0.00	0.00	\$ 25,027			
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. (0) OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)	2.50	0.00	0.00	25,027			
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL SCHOLARS	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
2. (14) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)	3.00	0.00	0.00	86,197			
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS				0			
4. (1) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS				1,000			
5. (2) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)				16,100			
6. (0) OTHER				0			
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)					128,324		
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)					48,763		
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)					177,087		
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT					0		
E. TRAVEL 1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)					28,250		
2. FOREIGN					0		
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS \$ _____				600			
2. TRAVEL _____				70,412			
3. SUBSISTENCE _____				62,115			
4. OTHER _____				0			
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (82) TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS					133,127		
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES				17,550			
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION				9,600			
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES				17,300			
4. COMPUTER SERVICES				9,000			
5. SUBAWARDS				146,503			
6. OTHER				93,374			
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS					293,327		
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)					631,791		
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE) Indirect cost rate calculated on total direct less subcontracts (Rate: 38.0000, Base: 485288)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)					184,409		
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)					816,200		
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS					0		
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)					\$ 816,200	\$	
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI/PI NAME Wendy K Warnick				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
ORG. REP. NAME* Wendy Warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
		Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG			

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET Cumulative

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR Wendy K Warnick				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PI, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-months		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
	CAL	ACAD	SUMR				
1. Wendy K Warnick - Executive Director	2.50	0.00	0.00	\$ 25,027			
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. () OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)	2.50	0.00	0.00	25,027			
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL SCHOLARS	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
2. (14) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)	3.00	0.00	0.00	86,197			
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS				0			
4. (1) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS				1,000			
5. (2) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)				16,100			
6. (0) OTHER				0			
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)					128,324		
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)					48,763		
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)					177,087		
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT					0		
E. TRAVEL					28,250		
1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)							
2. FOREIGN					0		
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS \$ _____			600				
2. TRAVEL _____			70,412				
3. SUBSISTENCE _____			62,115				
4. OTHER _____			0				
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (82)				TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS	133,127		
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES					17,550		
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION					9,600		
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6. OTHER					93,374		
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS					293,327		
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)					631,791		
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)					184,409		
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)					816,200		
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS					0		
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)					\$ 816,200	\$	
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI/PI NAME Wendy K Warnick				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
ORG. REP. NAME* Wendy Warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
		Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG			

C *ELECTRONIC SIGNATURES REQUIRED FOR REVISED BUDGET

This is a request for a supplement to ARCUS' cooperative agreement with the National Science Foundation (No. ARC-0101279). The supplement of \$816,200 to the funding already awarded is necessary to extend the expiration date of the award to 30 September 2007.

All of the activities described are in keeping with and part of ARCUS' work for the National Science Foundation (NSF) providing organizational support for the U.S. arctic science programs.

ARCUS is submitting this supplement request to continue activities at the request of and on behalf of NSF and the arctic research community, and other participants in and managers of arctic research programs. The activities and support to be provided have been discussed with the relevant NSF program managers.

Item A: Senior Personnel

Funding totaling \$25,027 for current staff through 30 September 2007 is requested.

Item B: Other Personnel

Resources are requested for a total of 17 staff positions for three additional months. Personnel salaries and benefits required to continue to develop, coordinate, and manage continuing activities total \$103,297.

Item C: Fringe Benefits

ARCUS charges actual fringe benefits costs on direct salaries. The fringe rate for budgeting purpose is 38% and totals \$48,763.

Items E and F: Travel and Participant Support

Additional resources are requested to support participation in several upcoming meetings: the *ARCSS Committee* meeting, the *SASS PI* meeting, the *SEARCH Science Steering Committee* meeting and a *STATE* community workshop. Additional support of three speakers for the Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series also is requested. Funds supporting travel is requested for a total of 82 participants at a cost of \$161,377.

Item G: Other Direct Costs

Line 1. Materials and Supplies

Resources totaling \$17,550 are requested to support typical materials costs for a three-month period.

Line 2. Publication/Documentation and Dissemination

Publication and distribution costs for documents including the recommendations from the *Arctic System Synthesis Workshop: New Perspectives through Data Discovery and Modeling*, the *Arctic Forum* abstract volume, and *Sustaining the Bering Ecosystem: A Social Sciences Research Plan* total \$9,600.

Line 3. Consultant Services

Consultant services costs totaling \$17,300 will support the ARCSS Committee, providing a renewal of the annual stipend for the ARCSS Committee chair.

Line 4. Computer Services

Computer support services totaling \$9,000 are anticipated under Core Support.

Line 5. Subcontracts

Continuation of subcontracts to support the ARCSS Program, including the HARC project office for one year (\$73,533—UAF), support for the ARCSS Committee chair for one year (\$35,082—UCSB), and the SNACS synthesis coordination for one year (\$37,888—CRREL) will cost \$146,503.

Line 6. Other

Resources totaling \$93,374 are requested to cover the cost of conference meeting support and other miscellaneous expenses for participants at the ARCSS committee meeting, the SEARCH Science Steering Committee meeting, the SASS PI meeting, and the STATE community workshop.

Item I: Indirect Costs (rate/base)

The ARCUS maximum provisional rate is currently 38%. The current ARCUS NSF cooperative agreement allows charging of indirect costs to Participant Support, which has been kept in the base of \$485,288.

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
 OPP-0101279
 Total Costs by Category

Attachment A

6/14/07 15:43

	6.5 Year Cumulative Budget	Year 6 Actual	1st Supplement Year 7 Estimate	2nd Supplement Year 7 Estimate
1 ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING				
1.1 Arctic Logistics	134,312	290	-	-
1.2 ALIAS Website	603,700	-	-	-
1.3 GIS Planning	66,420	4,625	-	-
1.4a SEARCH Planning	987,869	147,267	12,350	80,907
1.4b SEARCH OSM Student Support	28,776	-	-	-
1.5 Bering Sea Planning	218,684	57,128	2,690	3,104
1.6 Workshop TBD	-	-	-	-
1.7 SEARCH Brochure	5,735	-	-	-
1.8 Arctic Data Survey	7,485	-	-	-
SubTotal Direct Costs	2,052,981	209,310	15,040	84,011
Indirect Costs	793,428	74,681	5,715	31,924
TOTAL	2,846,409	283,991	20,755	115,935
2 NSF DIVISION OF ARCTIC SCIENCES COORDINATION				
2.1 <i>Division of Arctic Science Materials</i>	36,042	188	-	-
2.2 <i>ARCSS Program Coordination</i>				
2.2.1 ARCSS Coordination	1,892,259	290,521	129,920	372,873
2.2.2 ARCSS All-Hands Workshop	318,564	-	-	-
2.2.3 HARC SMO	185,753	-	-	-
2.2.4 Arctic Hydrology Report	18,275	-	-	-
SubTotal 2.2 Direct Costs	2,414,851	290,521	129,920	372,873
2.3 <i>ASSP Program Coordination</i>				
2.3.1 Arctic Social Sciences Planning	182,135	7,956	-	-
2.3.2 Greenland Book	12,263	-	-	-
2.3.3 Arctic Social Sciences Volume	35,886	-	-	-
2.3.4 Bering Sea Community Planning	81,671	277	-	9,950
SubTotal 2.3 Direct Costs	311,955	8,233	-	9,950
Sub-Total Direct Costs	2,762,848	298,944	129,920	382,823
Indirect Costs	833,136	77,785	49,370	89,802
TOTAL	3,595,984	376,729	179,290	472,625
3 ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION				
3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities	37,256	3,732	8,770	5,320
3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers Program	152,868	21,375	5,100	5,100
3.3 Arctic Science Education Report	42,275	-	-	-
3.4 ARCTIC ALIVE!	27,996	-	-	-
3.5 TREC	215,489	130,631	-	-
SubTotal Direct Costs	475,884	155,737	13,870	10,420
Indirect Costs	189,315	58,094	5,271	3,960
TOTAL	665,199	213,831	19,141	14,380
4 INFORMATION AND OUTREACH				
4.1 Witness the Arctic Newsletter	416,224	93,663	10,350	4,140
4.2 Web Site/Internet Resources	625,876	135,380	27,600	34,500
4.3 Arctic Info Listserv	110,615	33,020	7,866	8,556
4.4 Directory of Arctic Researchers	70,577	3,045	990	1,335
4.5 Internet Graphics Archive	121,259	35,329	6,900	8,970
4.6 Community Outreach	628,827	189,399	174,594	7,120
4.7 Publication: The Arctic	48,574	1,324	-	-
4.8 Endangered Species Bulletin	2,713	-	-	-
SubTotal Direct Costs	2,024,665	491,161	228,300	64,621
Indirect Costs	795,322	182,734	86,753	24,555
TOTAL	2,819,987	673,895	315,053	89,176
5 CORE SUPPORT				
Core Support				
SubTotal Direct Costs	1,702,577	318,839	71,850	89,916
Indirect Costs	676,118	119,419	27,303	34,168
TOTAL	2,378,695	438,258	99,153	124,084
TOTAL COSTS	12,306,274	1,986,704	633,392	816,200

NSF Task & Activity Summary

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	6.5 Year Cumulative Budget	Year 6 Actual	1st Supplement Year 7 Estimate	2nd Supplement Year 7 Estimate
1 Arctic Community Science Planning				
1.1 ARCTIC LOGISTICS				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	68,575	290	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	11,119	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	9,102	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	45,516	-	-	-
Total direct costs	134,312	290	-	-
Indirect Costs	56,451	110	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	190,763	400	-	-
1.2 ALIAS WEBSITE				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	395,481	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	66,172	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	5,747	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	1,254	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	135,046	-	-	-
Total direct costs	603,700	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	244,057	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	847,757	-	-	-
1.3 GIS PLANNING				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	39,175	4,612	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	5,548	13	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	9,688	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	12,009	-	-	-
Total direct costs	66,420	4,625	-	-
Indirect Costs	27,359	1,756	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	93,779	6,381	-	-
1.4a SEARCH PLANNING				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	367,298	41,693	10,350	15,180
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic and foreign)	67,179	15,693	2,000	7,500
Travel (foreign)	-	8,506	-	-
Participant Support Costs	199,361	36,845	-	29,202
Other Direct Costs	354,031	44,530	-	29,025
Total direct costs	987,869	147,267	12,350	80,907
Indirect Costs	360,016	51,660	4,693	30,745
Total direct and indirect costs	1,347,885	198,927	17,043	111,652

NSF Task & Activity Summary

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	<u>6.5 Year Cumulative Budget</u>	<u>Year 6 Actual</u>	<u>1st Supplement Year 7 Estimate</u>	<u>2nd Supplement Year 7 Estimate</u>
1.4b SEARCH OSM Student Support				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic and foreign)	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	27,945	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	831	-	-	-
Total direct costs	28,776	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	12,374	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	41,150	-	-	-
1.5 BERING SEA PLANNING				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	75,026	20,921	690	1,104
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	10,266	3,576	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	80,217	28,569	2,000	2,000
Other Direct Costs	53,175	4,062	-	-
Total direct costs	218,684	57,128	2,690	3,104
Indirect Costs	87,841	21,155	1,022	1,179
Total direct and indirect costs	306,525	78,283	3,712	4,283
1.7 SEARCH BROCHURE				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	1,083	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	4,652	-	-	-
Total direct costs	5,735	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	2,419	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	8,154	-	-	-
1.8 ARCTIC DATA SURVEY				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	235	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	7,250	-	-	-
Total direct costs	7,485	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	2,911	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	10,396	-	-	-

NSF Task & Activity Summary

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	6.5 Year Cumulative Budget	Year 6 Actual	1st Supplement Year 7 Estimate	2nd Supplement Year 7 Estimate
2 NSF Division of Arctic Sciences Coordination				
2.1 DIVISION OF ARCTIC SCIENCE MATERIALS				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	17,419	188	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	18,623	-	-	-
Total direct costs	36,042	188	-	-
Indirect Costs	14,877	71	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	50,919	260	-	-
2.2 ARCSS PROGRAM COORDINATION				
2.2.1 ARCSS COORDINATION				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	404,911	108,015	26,220	36,246
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	113,357	30,083	18,000	17,250
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	455,582	11,734	42,000	93,825
Other Direct Costs	918,409	140,689	43,700	225,552
Total direct costs	1,892,259	290,521	129,920	372,873
Indirect Costs	513,530	74,639	49,370	86,021
Total direct and indirect costs	2,405,789	365,160	179,290	458,894
2.2.2 ARCSS ALL-HANDS WORKSHOP				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	69,029	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	14,943	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	86,986	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	147,606	-	-	-
Total direct costs	318,564	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	134,401	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	452,965	-	-	-
2.2.3 HARC SMO				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	49,025	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	11,985	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	29,749	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	94,994	-	-	-
Total direct costs	185,753	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	78,111	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	263,864	-	-	-

NSF Task & Activity Summary

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	<u>6.5 Year Cumulative Budget</u>	<u>Year 6 Actual</u>	<u>1st Supplement Year 7 Estimate</u>	<u>2nd Supplement Year 7 Estimate</u>
2.2.4 ARCTIC HYDROLOGY REPORT				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	16,279	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	<u>1,996</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>
Total direct costs	18,275	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	<u>7,709</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u>25,984</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>
2.3 ASSP PROGRAM COORDINATION				
2.3.1 ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES WORKSHOP				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	35,433	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	6,308	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	5,560	6,003	-	-
Other Direct Costs	<u>134,834</u>	<u>1,953</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>
Total direct costs	182,135	7,956	-	-
Indirect Costs	<u>33,262</u>	<u>2,970</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u>215,397</u>	<u>10,926</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>
2.3.2 GREENLAND BOOK				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	1,326	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	<u>10,937</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>
Total direct costs	12,263	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	<u>5,172</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u>17,435</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>
2.3.3 ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES VOLUME				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	7,202	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	1,556	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	13,380	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	<u>13,748</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>
Total direct costs	35,886	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	<u>15,067</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u>50,953</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>

NSF Task & Activity Summary

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	6.5 Year Cumulative Budget	Year 6 Actual	1st Supplement Year 7 Estimate	2nd Supplement Year 7 Estimate
2.3.4 BERING SEA COMMUNITY PLANNING				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	29,489	277	-	3,450
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	3,540	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	19,136	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	29,506	-	-	6,500
Total direct costs	81,671	277	-	9,950
Indirect Costs	31,007	105	-	3,781
Total direct and indirect costs	112,678	382	-	13,731

3 Arctic Science Education**3.1 ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION ACTIVITIES**

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	22,458	-	5,520	2,070
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	739	2,071	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	6,547	1,626	3,000	3,000
Other Direct Costs	7,512	35	250	250
Total direct costs	37,256	3,732	8,770	5,320
Indirect Costs	15,104	1,418	3,333	2,022
Total direct and indirect costs	52,360	5,150	12,103	7,342

3.2 ARCTIC VISITING SPEAKERS PROGRAM

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	49,653	7,607	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	102,525	13,680	5,100	5,100
Other Direct Costs	690	89	-	-
Total direct costs	152,868	21,375	5,100	5,100
Indirect Costs	61,336	7,978	1,938	1,938
Total direct and indirect costs	214,204	29,352	7,038	7,038

3.3 ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION REPORT

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	10,633	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	458	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	31,184	-	-	-
Total direct costs	42,275	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	17,756	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	60,031	-	-	-

NSF Task & Activity Summary

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	<u>6.5 Year Cumulative Budget</u>	<u>Year 6 Actual</u>	<u>1st Supplement Year 7 Estimate</u>	<u>2nd Supplement Year 7 Estimate</u>
3.4 ARCTIC ALIVE				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	18,053	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	4,774	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	3,762	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	<u>1,407</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>
Total direct costs	27,996	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	<u>11,627</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u>39,623</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>

3.5 TREC				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	124,622	79,412	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	1,989	4,575	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	23,550	14,364	-	-
Other Direct Costs	<u>65,328</u>	<u>32,280</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>
Total direct costs	215,489	130,631	-	-
Indirect Costs	<u>83,492</u>	<u>48,698</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u>298,981</u>	<u>179,329</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>

4 Information and Outreach**4.1 WITNESS THE ARCTIC NEWSLETTERS**

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	219,545	60,318	10,350	4,140
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	794	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	<u>195,885</u>	<u>33,345</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>
Total direct costs	416,224	93,663	10,350	4,140
Indirect Costs	<u>166,763</u>	<u>34,946</u>	<u>3,933</u>	<u>1,573</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u>582,987</u>	<u>128,609</u>	<u>14,283</u>	<u>5,713</u>

4.2 INTERNET RESOURCES

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	554,158	124,731	27,600	34,500
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	21,889	10,171	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	<u>49,829</u>	<u>478</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>
Total direct costs	625,876	135,380	27,600	34,500
Indirect Costs	<u>246,030</u>	<u>50,653</u>	<u>10,488</u>	<u>13,110</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u>871,906</u>	<u>186,033</u>	<u>38,088</u>	<u>47,610</u>

NSF Task & Activity Summary

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	<u>6.5 Year Cumulative Budget</u>	<u>Year 6 Actual</u>	<u>1st Supplement Year 7 Estimate</u>	<u>2nd Supplement Year 7 Estimate</u>
4.3 ARCTIC INFO LISTSERVER				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	106,022	33,020	7,866	8,556
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	4,593	-	-	-
Total direct costs	110,615	33,020	7,866	8,556
Indirect Costs	43,747	12,347	2,989	3,251
Total direct and indirect costs	154,362	45,368	10,855	11,807

4.4 DIRECTORY OF ARCTIC RESEARCHERS

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	38,439	2,445	690	1,035
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	32,138	600	300	300
Total direct costs	70,577	3,045	990	1,335
Indirect Costs	28,369	1,139	376	507
Total direct and indirect costs	98,946	4,185	1,366	1,842

4.5 INTERNET GRAPHICS ARCHIVE

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	105,620	32,517	6,900	8,970
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	2,500	2,151	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	13,139	662	-	-
Total direct costs	121,259	35,329	6,900	8,970
Indirect Costs	46,718	13,232	2,622	3,409
Total direct and indirect costs	167,977	48,561	9,522	12,379

4.6 ARCTIC COMMUNITY OUTREACH

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	138,946	57,529	29,394	5,520
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	51,511	12,843	13,000	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	189,285	52,343	55,000	-
Other Direct Costs	249,085	66,683	77,200	1,600
Total direct costs	628,827	189,399	174,594	7,120
Indirect Costs	244,055	69,929	66,345	2,705
Total direct and indirect costs	872,882	259,328	240,939	9,825

NSF Task & Activity Summary

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	<u>6.5 Year Cumulative Budget</u>	<u>Year 6 Actual</u>	<u>1st Supplement Year 7 Estimate</u>	<u>2nd Supplement Year 7 Estimate</u>
4.7 PUBLICATION: THE ARCTIC				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	26,299	1,302	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	22,275	22	-	-
Total direct costs	48,574	1,324	-	-
Indirect Costs	18,497	487	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	67,071	1,812	-	-

4.8 ENDANGERED SPECIES BULLETIN

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	2,713	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	2,713	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	1,143	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	3,856	-	-	-

5 Core Support

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	1,073,501	187,140	44,850	56,316
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	95,540	14,088	5,500	3,500
Travel (foreign)	2,478	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	531,058	117,612	21,500	30,100
Total direct costs	1,702,577	318,839	71,850	89,916
Indirect Costs	676,118	119,419	27,303	34,168
Total direct and indirect costs	2,378,695	438,258	99,153	124,084

TOTAL PROGRAMS

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	4,067,648	762,017	170,430	177,087
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	491,709	95,262	38,500	28,250
Travel (foreign)	8,225	8,506	-	-
Participant Support Costs	1,264,087	165,165	107,100	133,127
Other Direct Costs	3,187,286	443,040	142,950	293,327
Total direct costs	9,018,955	1,473,991	458,980	631,791
Indirect Costs	3,287,319	512,713	174,412	184,409
Total direct and indirect costs	12,306,274	1,986,704	633,392	816,200

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
 OPP-0101279
 NSF Program Summary

Attachment C

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<u>Form 1030 Category</u>		<u>6.5 Year Cumulative Budget</u>	<u>YEAR 6 YTD Actual</u>	<u>1st YEAR 7 Supplement</u>	<u>2nd YEAR 7 Supplement</u>
Salaries					
President	A1	-	-	-	-
Executive director	A2	458,112	74,168	19,000	25,027
Other professionals	B2	2,188,811	366,408	82,200	86,197
Student	B3	58,756	17,054	2,800	1,000
Clerical	B5	304,484	84,112	19,500	16,100
Total salaries		<u>3,010,162</u>	<u>541,741</u>	<u>123,500</u>	<u>128,324</u>
Fringe Benefits	C	1,057,485	220,276	46,930	48,763
Total salaries and fringe benefits		<u>4,067,647</u>	<u>762,017</u>	<u>170,430</u>	<u>177,087</u>
Permanent Equipment	D	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	E1	491,709	95,262	38,500	28,250
Travel (foreign)	E2	8,225	8,506	-	-
Participant Support Costs					
Stipends	F1	51,038	4,300	600	600
Travel	F2	597,662	90,641	56,000	70,412
Subsistence	F3	615,387	70,224	50,500	62,115
Total participant costs		<u>1,264,087</u>	<u>165,165</u>	<u>107,100</u>	<u>133,127</u>
Other Direct Costs					
Materials and supplies	G1	364,173	58,692	16,650	17,550
Publication cost/ docum/dissem	G2	560,004	50,146	7,500	9,600
Consultant services	G3	602,795	56,498	10,800	17,300
Computer services	G4	70,108	24,691	6,000	9,000
Subcontracts	G5	714,536	102,003	-	146,503
Other	G6	875,670	151,010	102,000	93,374
Total other direct costs		<u>3,187,286</u>	<u>443,039</u>	<u>142,950</u>	<u>293,327</u>
Total direct costs	H	9,018,955	1,473,991	458,980	631,791
Indirect	I	3,287,319	512,712	174,412	184,409
TOTAL	J	<u><u>12,306,274</u></u>	<u><u>1,986,704</u></u>	<u><u>633,392</u></u>	<u><u>816,200</u></u>

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET YEAR 1

ORGANIZATION Cold Regions Laboratory Inc				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PI, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-months		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
				CAL	ACAD	SUMR	
1.				0.00	0.00	0.00	\$
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. (0) OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)				0.00	0.00	0.00	0
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)				0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL SCHOLARS				0.00	0.00	0.00	0
2. (0) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)				4.00	0.00	0.00	20,000
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS							0
4. (0) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS							0
5. (0) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)							0
6. (0) OTHER							0
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)							20,000
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)							7,450
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)							27,450
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT							0
E. TRAVEL 1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)							0
2. FOREIGN							0
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS \$ _____							0
2. TRAVEL _____							0
3. SUBSISTENCE _____							0
4. OTHER _____							0
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (0) TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS							0
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES							0
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION							0
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES							0
4. COMPUTER SERVICES							0
5. SUBAWARDS							0
6. OTHER							0
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS							0
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)							27,450
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE) (Rate: 38.0260, Base: 28 (Rate: 38.0260, Base: 27450)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)							10,438
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)							37,888
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS							0
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)							\$ 37,888 \$
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI/PD NAME				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
ORG. REP. NAME* Wendy Warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
				Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG	

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET Cumulative

ORGANIZATION Cold Regions Laboratory Inc				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PI, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-months		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
				CAL	ACAD	SUMR	
1.				0.00	0.00	0.00	\$
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. () OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)				0.00	0.00	0.00	0
7. (0) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)				0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL SCHOLARS				0.00	0.00	0.00	0
2. (0) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)				4.00	0.00	0.00	20,000
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS							0
4. (0) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS							0
5. (0) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)							0
6. (0) OTHER							0
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)							20,000
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)							7,450
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)							27,450
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT							0
E. TRAVEL 1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)							0
2. FOREIGN							0
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS \$ _____							0
2. TRAVEL _____							0
3. SUBSISTENCE _____							0
4. OTHER _____							0
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (0) TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS							0
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES							0
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION							0
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES							0
4. COMPUTER SERVICES							0
5. SUBAWARDS							0
6. OTHER							0
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS							0
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)							27,450
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)							10,438
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)							37,888
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS							0
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)							\$ 37,888 \$
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI/PD NAME				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
ORG. REP. NAME* Wendy Warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
				Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG	

C *ELECTRONIC SIGNATURES REQUIRED FOR REVISED BUDGET

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET YEAR 1

ORGANIZATION University of Alaska Fairbanks Campus				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PI, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-months		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
		CAL	ACAD	SUMR			
1.		0.00	0.00	0.00	\$	\$	
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. (0) OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)		0.00	0.00	0.00		0	
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)		0.00	0.00	0.00		0	
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL SCHOLARS		0.00	0.00	0.00		0	
2. (0) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)		2.00	0.00	0.00		17,018	
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS						0	
4. (0) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS						0	
5. (0) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)						0	
6. (0) OTHER						0	
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)						17,018	
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)						11,095	
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)						28,113	
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT						0	
E. TRAVEL 1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)						3,940	
2. FOREIGN						11,800	
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS \$ _____						0	
2. TRAVEL _____						0	
3. SUBSISTENCE _____						0	
4. OTHER _____						0	
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (0)				TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS		0	
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES						1,000	
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION						2,500	
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES						0	
4. COMPUTER SERVICES						0	
5. SUBAWARDS						0	
6. OTHER						2,500	
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS						6,000	
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)						49,853	
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE) (Rate: 47.5000, Base: 49853) (Rate: 47.5000, Base: 49853)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)						23,680	
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)						73,533	
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS						0	
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)						\$ 73,533 \$	
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI/PD NAME				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
ORG. REP. NAME* Wendy Warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
		Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG			

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET Cumulative

ORGANIZATION University of Alaska Fairbanks Campus				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR				AWARD NO.			
				Proposed	Granted		
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-months		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
				CAL	ACAD	SUMR	
1.				0.00	0.00	0.00	\$
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. (0) OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)				0.00	0.00	0.00	0
7. (0) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)				0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL SCHOLARS				0.00	0.00	0.00	0
2. (0) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)				2.00	0.00	0.00	17,018
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS							0
4. (0) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS							0
5. (0) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)							0
6. (0) OTHER							0
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)							17,018
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)							11,095
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)							28,113
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT							0
E. TRAVEL							3,940
1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)							
2. FOREIGN							11,800
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS \$ _____				0			
2. TRAVEL _____				0			
3. SUBSISTENCE _____				0			
4. OTHER _____				0			
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (0)							
TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS							0
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES							1,000
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION							2,500
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES							0
4. COMPUTER SERVICES							0
5. SUBAWARDS							0
6. OTHER							2,500
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS							6,000
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)							49,853
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)							23,680
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)							73,533
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS							0
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)							\$ 73,533 \$
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI/PD NAME ORG. REP. NAME* Wendy Warnick				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
		Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG			

C *ELECTRONIC SIGNATURES REQUIRED FOR REVISED BUDGET

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET YEAR 1

ORGANIZATION University of California - Santa Barbara				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PI, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-months		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
				CAL	ACAD	SUMR	
1.				0.00	0.00	0.00	\$
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. (0) OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)				0.00	0.00	0.00	0
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)				0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL SCHOLARS				0.00	0.00	0.00	0
2. (0) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)				3.00	0.00	0.00	30,000
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS							0
4. (0) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS							0
5. (0) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)							0
6. (0) OTHER							0
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)							30,000
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)							5,082
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)							35,082
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT							0
E. TRAVEL 1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)							0
2. FOREIGN							0
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS	\$		0				
2. TRAVEL			0				
3. SUBSISTENCE			0				
4. OTHER			0				
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (0)				TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS			0
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES							0
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION							0
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES							0
4. COMPUTER SERVICES							0
5. SUBAWARDS							0
6. OTHER							0
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS							0
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)							35,082
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE) (Rate: , Base:)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)							0
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)							35,082
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS							0
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)							\$ 35,082 \$
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI/PD NAME				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
ORG. REP. NAME*				Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG	
Wendy Warnick							

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET Cumulative

ORGANIZATION University of California - Santa Barbara				FOR NSF USE ONLY					
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)				
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR				AWARD NO.					
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-months					
				CAL	ACAD	SUMR	Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)	
1.				0.00	0.00	0.00	\$	\$	
2.									
3.									
4.									
5.									
6. () OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)				0.00	0.00	0.00		0	
7. (0) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)				0.00	0.00	0.00		0	
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)									
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL SCHOLARS				0.00	0.00	0.00		0	
2. (0) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)				3.00	0.00	0.00		30,000	
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS									
4. (0) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS									
5. (0) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)									
6. (0) OTHER									
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)									30,000
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)									5,082
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)									35,082
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)									
TOTAL EQUIPMENT									0
E. TRAVEL									0
1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)									0
2. FOREIGN									0
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS									
1. STIPENDS \$ _____									0
2. TRAVEL _____									0
3. SUBSISTENCE _____									0
4. OTHER _____									0
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (0)				TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS				0	
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS									
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES									0
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION									0
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES									0
4. COMPUTER SERVICES									0
5. SUBAWARDS									0
6. OTHER									0
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS									0
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)									35,082
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE)									
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)									0
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)									35,082
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS									0
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)									\$ 35,082
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$					
PI/PD NAME ORG. REP. NAME* Wendy Warnick				FOR NSF USE ONLY					
				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION					
				Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG			